

CDE4Peace

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CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT AND EXPERIMENTATION FOR EU CONFLICT PREVENTION AND PEACE-BUILDING (CDE4PEACE)

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Working paper on operational concepts

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Executive Summary

This Working paper presents a review of the operational concepts of three EU Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) missions: EULEX Kosovo, EUTM Mali and EUBAM Libya. The desk review has been carried out under WP3 (Review) of the CDE4Peace project. The missions have been selected to provide diversity of the operational concepts' review in terms of mission goals, mandates and geographical locations. The Working paper seeks to extract the main features of the EU operational concepts for a potential application in quantitative research. A method for decomposing and converting operational concepts into quantifiable variables by means of peace indicators is elaborated.

1. Introduction

Operational concepts govern the planning and conduct of concrete peacebuilding operations and / or missions. After 20 years of the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) the EU has conducted more than 35 missions and operations using civilian and military instruments. This Working paper presents a review of the operational concepts of three concrete EU CSDP missions: EULEX Kosovo, EUTM Mali and EUBAM Libya. The operational concepts' review is based on an analysis of publicly available primary and secondary sources (EU Council Decisions, official web-sites, case study reports, databases, media publications etc.). The concept-scoping gives answer to the research question: What are the features of operational concepts in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding? After extracting the main concept features the Working paper explores the possibility for converting some structural components of the operational concepts into quantifiable variables which could have applied research applications. This would provide an important (and missing) methodological link between the qualitative research methods from conflict and peace studies and quantitative, experimentation tools (including tools for concept development and experimentation - CDE).

The review of operational concepts in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding is focussed on the key policy and operational documents of three concrete EU CSDP missions: EULEX Kosovo (the largest EU civilian CSDP mission), EUTM Mali (military CSDP training mission) and EUBAM Libya (civilian CSDP border management assistance mission). The missions have been selected to provide diversity of the operational concepts' review in terms of mission goals, mandates and geographical locations. It should be noted that in EU terminology civilian CSDP interventions are called 'missions', regardless of whether they have an executive mandate or a non-executive mandate. Military interventions can either have an executive mandate in which case they are referred to as 'operations' or non-executive mandate in which case they are called 'missions'. All three EU interventions under review in this Working paper are 'missions' in EU terminology, nevertheless they have the full set of operational documents required in the CSDP policy process. In this case 'mission concepts' are identical with operational concepts. Hence, the terms mission and operational concepts are used interchangeably in the Working paper.

The operational concepts of CSDP missions and operations are framed by a number of documents drafted by EU bodies and adopted by Member States in the Council. The main documents are the Crisis Management Concept (CMC), Military or Civilian Strategic Options (MSOs/CSOs), the respective Council Decision, the Concepts of Operations (CONOPS), and the Operation Plan (OPLAN). Not all of these documents are always required and some steps may be skipped when rapid response is needed.¹ The CMC is the first operational document which explains what to do, why, where and with whom and sets out the overall parameters of a mission / operation. The CONOPS is a concise statement of how the Operation Commander intends to fulfil his mission, whereas the OPLAN is the highly detailed script of the operation in its entirety. Both the CONOPS and the OPLAN have to be approved by the EUMC (European Union Military Committee), the Political and Security Committee (PSC) and the Council. The CMC, CONOPS, the OPLAN and the Council Decision frame the operational concept in the EU context as a credible research subject.

¹ Yves de Kermabon, 'Crisis Management Procedures', in *Handbook for Decisionmakers. The Common Security and Defence Policy of the EU*, ed. Jochen Rechrl (Vienna: Federal Ministry of Defence and Sports of the Republic of Austria, 2014), 45-47.

2. EULEX Kosovo operational concept

The European Union Rule of Law Mission in Kosovo (EULEX) was launched in 2008 as the largest and the longest running civilian mission under the Common Security and Defence Policy of the EU.² The mandate of EULEX is based on Security Council Resolution 1244, Council Joint Action 2008/124/CFSP of 4 February 2008³, and numerous follow-up Council Decisions. According to the mission statement in Art.2 of the Joint Action, EULEX Kosovo ‘shall assist the Kosovo institutions, judicial authorities and law enforcement agencies in their progress towards sustainability and accountability and in further developing and strengthening an independent multi-ethnic justice system and multi-ethnic police and customs service, ensuring that these institutions are free from political interference and adhering to internationally recognized standards and European best practices’. The Joint Action then ‘translates’ the mission mandate into a number of operational tasks horizontally for the three different components of EULEX, i.e. the justice, police and customs components. Within its current mandate (as of October 2020) EULEX Kosovo undertakes monitoring activities and has limited executive functions. EULEX Kosovo implements its mandate through Monitoring and Operations pillars. The Mission maintains a limited residual capacity as a second security responder and provides support to Kosovo Police’s crowd and riot control capability.

EULEX Kosovo is considered a unique and unprecedented EU mission due to its unparalleled staff size (about 2500 staff members in 2009) and its executive mandate. Conceptually EULEX Kosovo is seen in the context of other police missions in the Western Balkans, most notably EUPM in Bosnia and Herzegovina and EUPOL Proxima in Macedonia.⁴ An important EU conceptual document in this respect is the Comprehensive concept for ESDP police strengthening missions.⁵ Indeed, the operational concept of rule of law missions could also be linked with the strategic concept of the EU as ‘a civilian power’.⁶ This link, however, is not direct; it could be argued that to great extent the international setting and the specific needs of the situation on the ground have shaped the mandate of the EULEX Kosovo mission which took over executive justice functions from UNMIK (UN Interim Administration Mission in Kosovo). Moreover, the mission’s mandate was constantly evolving to integrate new challenges.

As argued by Zupančič and Pejič the executive mandate of EULEX is in line with the EU’s normative character; the Union presents itself as ‘a force for good’, using the instruments of peacebuilding as a way of building its image as a normative actor.⁷ The concept of ‘normative power Europe’ was developed by Manners who argues that EU principles or norms (the centrality of peace; liberty;

² See the official webpage of EULEX Kosovo at: <https://www.eulex-kosovo.eu/?page=2,1>

³ Council Joint Action 2008/124/CFSP of 4 February 2008 on the European Union Rule of Law Mission in Kosovo, EULEX Kosovo, OJ 2008 L 42.

⁴ Martina Spornbauer, *EULEX Kosovo – Mandate, Structure and Implementation: Essential Clarifications for an Unprecedented EU Mission* (The Hague: Centre for the Law of EU External Relations, 2010, Working paper no.5) 6.

⁵ Comprehensive Concept for ESDP Police Strengthening Missions: Interface with Broader Rule of Law, Council of the EU 15031/09 (Brussels, 26 October 2009).

⁶ Francois Duchêne, ‘Europe’s Role in World Peace’, in *Europe Tomorrow. Sixteen Europeans Look Ahead*, ed. Richard Mayne, (London: Fontana/Collins, 1972), 32-47.

⁷ Rok Zupančič and Nina Pejič, *Limits to the European Union’s Normative Power in a Post-conflict Society. EULEX and Peacebuilding in Kosovo* (Springer, 2018). 83-116.

democracy; supranational rule of law; and human rights) differentiate the Union from other political entities and incline it to act in a normative way.⁸ However, research on the perceptions of local residents in the post-conflict Kosovo society shows that the ability of the EU to project normative power is questioned on the ground. EULEX Kosovo has been subject to criticism with regard to deficiencies in the planning and implementation of the mission's mandate.⁹ There have also been accusations of corruption among EU staff members. The negative perception of the mission is explained by the double proximity paradox in peacebuilding in the context of the limits of the 'normative power Europe' concept.¹⁰

EULEX lacks a clear end-state or exit strategy which is the reason many local people perceive it as 'eternal' and without feasible goals. In fact, EULEX's CONOPS and OPLAN do not include an exit strategy. As noted in an audit report, the EULEX Concept of Operations (CONOPS) and Operation Plan (OPLAN), the basic planning documents for implementing the mission, do not contain clear benchmarks and objectively verifiable indicators to assess progress in meeting the mission's objectives.¹¹

3. EUTM Mali operational concept

The European Union Training Mission (EUTM) Mali was established in 2013 in response to the deteriorating security situation in the country and at the request of the Malian government. The mission's operational concept is legally based on Council Decisions which are public¹² and operational documents such as the Crisis Management Concept and Mission Plan which are classified. EUTM Mali is a military training mission which shall provide military and training advice to the Malian Armed Forces in order to contribute to the restoration of their military capacity. The mission shall not be involved in combat operations, which is just another example of a risk averse mandate characteristic for the EU. In the last EUTM-related Council Decision the mission mandate was broadened and extended.¹³ EUTM Mali is a military capacity-building mission whose objectives are the provision of training support to the Malian Armed Forces and military assistance to the G5 Sahel Joint Force as well as national armed forces in the G5 Sahel countries. With 570 staff members it was the largest EU non-executive mission. EUTM Mali is promoted as part of the EU's integrated approach to security and development in the Sahel.¹⁴

⁸ Ian Manners, 'Normative Power Europe: A Contradiction in Terms', *Journal of Common Market Studies* 40, no.2 (2002): 235-258.

⁹ Zupančič and Pejič, *Limits to the European Union's Normative Power in a Post-conflict Society*, 69-70.

¹⁰ Kari M. Osland and Mateja Peter, 'The Double Proximity Paradox in Peacebuilding: Implementation and Perception of the EU Rule of Law Mission in Kosovo', *European Security* 28, no.4 (2019): 493-512.

¹¹ European Court of Auditors, Special report no.18/2012 on the European Union Assistance to Kosovo Related to the Rule of Law' (Luxembourg, 2012), 29.

¹² Council Decision 2013/34/CFSP of 17 January 2013 and Council Decision 2013/87/CFSP of 18 February 2013.

¹³ Council Decision (CFSP) 2020/434 of 23 March 2020

¹⁴ Press release of the Council of the EU on the new Council Decision regarding EUTM Mali, 23 March 2020.

EUTM Mali is interpreted mostly in the context of security sector reform (SSR).¹⁵ It is considered one of the most important leverages for the EU in the area of SSR in Mali. In practical terms, one of the achievements of the mission in developing military capabilities was a training module on checkpoint security. This exemplifies a characteristic technical aspect of EU peacebuilding missions / operations. On the other hand, although not explicitly stated in policy and operational documents EUTM Mali's operational concept is shaped by geopolitical factors in the Sahel. The geopolitical interests of one EU Member State in Mali, both its historical past as a colonial power and currently through the substantial national military presence on the ground are considered a crucial factor for the overall engagement of the EU.¹⁶ This is to indicate that operational concepts are by no means given in full form in policy and operational documents, be them classified. In a certain sense operational concepts need to be constructed by the observer. And, paradoxically, the missing elements are essential parts of an operational concept.

EUTM Mali is critically assessed as another example of international intervention that may be well-intended, but that ends up producing very mixed results on the ground.¹⁷ One of the conclusions from the mission refers to the inability of the EU (and other international actors) to understand how key concepts such as SSR are understood on the ground. Highly problematic was also the ability to translate EU policies and Brussels-developed mandate into policies that make sense to the people on the ground. Empirical research suggests that overall, the EU's policy in Mali suffers from limited conflict sensitivity.¹⁸ The EU's approach in Mali seems short-term in nature. Research on strategic command and control of EUTM Mali suggests that the mission has played a role in testing an important EU bureaucratic concept, the establishment of the Military Planning and Conduct Capability (MPCC) after 2017.¹⁹ This is to exemplify the multiple ways concepts interact in the EU policy process.

EUTM Mali along with the EU civilian training mission EUCAP Sahel Mali have been frozen after the military coup in the country in August 2020. Speculations for EU responsibility for inadvertently helping to train the coup plotters have not been corroborated.²⁰

¹⁵ Moussa Djiré, Djibril Sow, Kissima Gakou, Bakary Camara, *WOSCAP D3.3 Assessing the EU's conflict prevention and peacebuilding interventions in Mali* (Bamako: Université des Sciences Juridiques et Politiques de Bamako, 2016), 41-60.

¹⁶ Morten Bøås, Abdoul Wahab Cissé, Aboubacar Diallo, Bård Drange, Frida Kvamme and Eva Stambøl, *EUNPACK D7.4 Working paper on implementation of EU crisis response in Mali* (Oslo: Norwegian Institute of International Affairs, 2018), 6.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, 5.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, 15-16.

¹⁹ Yf Reykers, 'A Permanent Headquarters under Construction? The Military Planning and Conduct Capability (MPCC) as a Proximate Principal', *Journal of European Integration* 41, no.6 (2019): 783-799.

²⁰ EU freezes Mali training missions after military coup, denies responsibility, EURACTIV.com with Reuters, 27/08/2020.

4. EUBAM Libya operational concept

The EU Integrated Border Management Assistance Mission in Libya (EUBAM Libya) was deployed under the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy in 2013. EUBAM Libya was officially promoted as part of the EU's comprehensive approach.²¹ From a geopolitical perspective EUBAM's operational concept was developed as a response to the rising problem of illegal migration in the Mediterranean and the related security concerns of a particular EU Member State.²² According to the Council Decision for the establishment of EUBAM Libya, the mission's objectives are to support the Libyan authorities to develop capacity for enhancing the security of Libya's borders in the short term and to develop a broader strategic Integrated Border Management (IBM) concept in the longer term.²³ Once again, a concept refers to another concept in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. The mission's mandate is focussed on training, mentoring, advisory and support in the area of border management. The mission is civilian and shall not carry out any executive function. Actually, EUBAM Libya is one of the smallest CSDP missions with 165 staff members at full operational capacity, which was actually never reached. After the security situation in Libya deteriorated in 2014, the mission was evacuated in Tunis and subsequently put on hold. In 2016 EUBAM's mandate was amended to include capacity building and SSR advice,²⁴ but as a result of protracted insecurity the mission barely shifted its position from being on hold.

The operational concept of EUBAM Libya with the ambition for an Integrated Border Management (IBM) concept and SSR is a clear example of an over-optimistic concept crushed by the political reality of a collapsing security situation.²⁵ It is a clash between a good-looking capacity-building concept and the harsh geopolitical realities on the ground. Small wonder that the accomplishments of the mission are assessed as modest. Buy-in for the acclaimed IBM concept and SSR was not present in Libyan authorities. Moreover, journalist investigations have claimed that human rights violations in detention centres had been conducted by Libyan forces trained by EUBAM Libya.²⁶ Although unproven, such allegations further undermine the EU's image as a normative power.

As a result of the concept-scoping the main features of operational concepts could be extracted, as shown on table 1.

²¹ Press release from the EEAS on EUBAM Libya, January 2015. Available at: https://eeas.europa.eu/archives/docs/csdp/missions-and-operations/eubam-libya/pdf/factsheet_eubam_libya_en.pdf

²² IECEU D3.4 The Libya Review (Helsinki: Crisis Management Centre, 2017), 43.

²³ Council Decision 2013/233/CFSP of 22 May 2013.

²⁴ Council Decision (CFSP) 2016/207 of 15 February 2016.

²⁵ For an assessment of the mission, see: IECEU D3.4 The Libya Review (Helsinki: Crisis Management Centre, 2017).

²⁶ Andrew Rettman, 'EU 'civilian' mission training paramilitaries in Libya', *EUobserver*, 18 Nov. 2013.

	Type of mission	Mandate	Capabilities	Components	Deficits	Links with concepts	Exit strategy
EULEX Kosovo	Executive, rule of law civilian mission	Monitoring, mentoring and advising (MMA) and executive mandate	Monitoring, operational functions and technical support	Justice, Police and Customs components	Deficiencies in the planning and implementation; Alleged corruption; lack of accountability and local ownership	'normative power' concept; 'civilian power' concept;	Broadly defined in terms of normative ends.
EUTM Mali	Training military non-executive mission	Military capacity-building in Mali and the G5 Sahel countries	Command and control, logistical chain and human resources	Education and training; Advisory; Force Protection and Medical components	Limited conflict sensitivity; short-term approach	Integrated approach; Security sector reform	Not clearly defined.
EUBAM Libya	Training civilian non-executive mission	Support for border management	Training, mentoring, advisory and support; Project capability	Border security	Over-optimistic goals; short lifespan; possible links with human rights violations	comprehensive approach; Integrated border management concept; SSR	Not clearly defined.

Table 1. Mission / operational concepts' features

The concept-scoping shows that mandates are pivotal in operational concepts. The mandates actually represent the EU's intentions; and the deficits in the operational concepts reveal the gaps between mandates (intentions) and implementation on the ground. Mission and operation mandates are usually over-ambitious which has attracted strong criticism and calls for a more realist approach.²⁷ Moreover, hidden objectives and national interests of particular EU Member States are attributed to some missions. On the other hand, links between mandates and strategic concepts are declared which are not fully substantiated. The introduction of quantifiable indicators for measuring mandates' performance and implementation could be helpful for defining more realistic mandates and clear exit strategies. Very importantly, quantification methods could be used in the planning phase to carry out a scientific assessment of alternative options for mandates (e.g. executive vs. non-executive mandate, civilian vs. military or civil-military missions/operations).

²⁷ See, for example: Morten Bøås and Pernille Rieker, *EUNPACK Executive Summary of the Final Report and Selected Policy Recommendations* (Brussels: Centre for European Policy Studies, March 2019), 13.

5. Quantification of mission / operational concepts and its limitations

In principle the CDE4Peace method for decomposing and converting operational concepts into quantifiable variables is closely connected with the project's quantification method for strategic concepts as defined in D3.1. Working paper on strategic concepts.²⁸ However, some important distinctions need to be made. Unlike strategic concepts, operational concepts are centred around mandates. The mandates describe what actually the operation / mission has to achieve. Mandates are logically converted into operation / mission goals and tasks. Moreover, the goals and tasks of a mission / operation are usually specified in the mandate as set out in the respective Council Decision. Therefore, converting mandates into goals and tasks is a most natural analytical process. Despite the high number of EU missions and operations and the multiple goals defined throughout 20 years of CSDP the mission goals could be categorized. For example, in the EU's Global Engagement Database²⁹ the goals of the missions / operations are categorized according to five categories, as follows:

- Border control – defines missions and operations aimed at monitoring and controlling borders;
- Security – missions and operations aimed at providing security and pacification;
- Support for policy reforms – missions and operations aimed at supporting policy reforms, mainly in the military and police sectors;
- Personnel training in the target country;
- Compliance with agreements between the parties in a conflict.

Mission/operational tasks are derived from the mission/operational goals and are usually set out in the respective Council Decision and the planning documents. In practice goals and tasks overlap. As argued in a research report from the EU-CIVCAP project, the EU has deployed relatively focussed civilian missions and the missions' mandates tend to be focussed.³⁰ An average EU mission in 2015 was mandated 2.18 tasks. The most common task was support to police, followed by security sector reform (SSR), border management, anti-terrorism (anti-piracy), support to judiciary / penitentiary, mediation and confidence building, support to armed forces and monitoring. It should be noted that although the number of tasks is not high, the scope of every single tasks is very broad and challenging.

As a next step mission goals and tasks must be converted into peace indicators which are quantifiable variables. The proposed CDE4Peace method for decomposing operational concepts into quantifiable variables is shown on fig.1.

²⁸ Nikolay Pavlov, *CDE4Peace D3.1 Working paper on strategic concepts* (Vienna: SYNYO GmbH, 2020).

²⁹ Danilo Di Mauro, Ulrich Krotz, and Katerina Wriarth. 2017. *EU's Global Engagement: A Database of CSDP Military Operations and Civilian Missions Worldwide*, Version 2.0, European University Institute (EUI). doi:10.2870/14148. p.30., available from: <https://globalgovernanceprogramme.eui.eu/research-project/eu-global-engagement-database/>

³⁰ Hylke Dijkstra, Petar Petrov, and Ewa Mahr (2016), 'Reacting to Conflict: Civilian Capabilities in the EU, UN and OSCE', *EU-CIVCAP Report*, DL4.1, pp.18-19, available from: <https://eu-civcap.net/portfolio/deliverables/>.

Fig.1 Method for decomposing and converting operational concepts into quantifiable variables

The quantification of EU operational concepts is very useful in practical terms as quantifiable variables are meaningful to software tools, including tools for concept development and experimentation (CDE). The added value of quantification is in that it enhances the scientific credibility of future research in this area and makes possible an important (and missing) methodological link between qualitative research methods from conflict and peace studies and quantitative methods and tools. Operational / mission concepts are an important research unit which could be further explored by the proposed quantification method.

Peace indicators play a crucial role in the CDE4Peace quantification method of EU operational / mission concepts. To a certain extent the work on peace indicators in the CDE4Peace project draws on the variables and indicators defined in the EU's Global Engagement Database.³¹ This first attempt to develop a centralized, comprehensive and accurate database on the EU CSDP missions and operations was made by the European University Institute in 2016-2017. The database developers have adequately addressed the challenges of data collection on CSDP missions and operations, including problems with data availability and fragmentation. The database's main contribution is the credible definition of 73 variables and indicators. Variables report data on: mission duration, EU Member State participation, personnel, goals, level of engagement, conflict intensity and budget. Data collection is based on data triangulation which is credible in scientific terms. One of the database's shortcomings is that no variables on mission impact are defined. This shortcoming could be overcome by employing the CDE4Peace method with peace indicators.

Peace indicators are suitable for measuring the impact from EU missions and operations under the CSDP. They allow for measuring the attainment of mission goals and the accomplishment of mission tasks. The CDE4Peace method regards missions / operations as large-scale projects which could be objectively evaluated by means of peace indicators. Peace indicators in the CDE4Peace method entail three main components, as follows:

- 1) Expert assessments;
- 2) Public perception surveys; and

³¹ Danilo Di Mauro, Ulrich Krotz, and Katerina Wriarth. 2017. *EU's Global Engagement: A Database of CSDP Military Operations and Civilian Missions Worldwide*, Version 2.0, European University Institute (EUI).

3) Peace data on mission impact.

The integration of the three components lends scientific reliability to the proposed quantification method for EU operational concepts. Expert assessments are a traditional approach for informed and knowledge-based evaluation of complex phenomena. Some of the key requirements in the assessment process are the choice of independent experts, high level of competence and lack of conflict of interests.

Public perception surveys must display quantitatively the perceptions of local populations towards EU missions and operations. The first attempt to conduct such public perception surveys in conflict-stricken target countries - albeit with a relatively small sample size - has been made under the EU H2020 research project EUNPACK (A conflict-sensitive unpacking of the EU comprehensive approach to conflict and crisis mechanisms).³² It is worth noting that local perceptions might differ from expert assessments in some respects. While this might complicate the research process, it is nevertheless welcome in terms of rigorous data triangulation.

Peace data on mission impact is the third key element of peace indicators, which makes possible defining trends and measuring violence levels in the respective conflict-stricken countries where an EU mission / operation is deployed. High-quality peace data might be regarded as evidence in the evaluation and judgement of mission / operational concepts. As a minimum peace data should include data on:

- the number of victims from a conflict for a given period after a mission / operation has been launched compared with the number for the same period before mission launch;
- the number of affected persons and casualties for a given period after a mission / operation has been launched compared with the number for the same period before mission launch;
- disruptions of critical infrastructures as a result of a conflict (before and after the start of a mission / operation for a given period);
- number of trained personnel under a mission / operation;
- communications between the conflicting parties facilitated by a mission / operation;
- number of homes and critical infrastructures renovated with the support of the respective EU mission / operation;

Sources for peace data collection could be national statistics, UN Statistics Division³³, NGO reports, EU Institute for Security Studies CSDP Mission Map³⁴, SIPRI³⁵, the IISS Military Balance³⁶, ReliefWeb³⁷, Uppsala Conflict Data Program³⁸ etc. The collection of peace data in the CDE4Peace method should also be based on data triangulation.

Aggregating the results from expert assessments, public perception surveys and peace data allows for calculating the mission's peace indicators. The process could be reiterated for greater precision of the results. The peace indicators could be compared with the indicators of alternative mission /

³² Website: <http://www.eunpack.eu/>

³³ Website: <https://unstats.un.org/home/>

³⁴ Website: <https://www.iiss.europa.eu/>

³⁵ Website: <https://www.sipri.org/>

³⁶ Website: <https://www.iiss.org/publications/the-military-balance>

³⁷ Website: <https://reliefweb.int/>

³⁸ Website: <https://ucdp.uu.se/>

operational concepts. For example, this would allow for comparing the peace indicators of executive vs. non-executive operational concepts, civilian vs. military or civil-military missions / operations.

Similar to other quantification methods the CDE4Peace method has its limitations. The use of formal statistical methods can hardly capture the multitude of data and relationships in a conflict. The CDE4Peace project takes into account the limitations of quantitative work as specified by Ron Smith who argues that quantitative peace research could be improved if authors put more emphasis on the substantive issues and less on the mechanical application of rule-based, statistical techniques.³⁹ The meaningful application of the proposed quantification method would be possible only if high-quality peace data is collected and processed in a politically unbiased way. Another limitation is that the quantification method cannot fully capture the causal links between EU missions and conflict trends on the ground. It is not a silver bullet for solving all deficits of EU missions and operations but it can help strengthen their conceptual foundations in a scientific and evidence-based way.

Quantification of operational concepts is not an end in itself. Quantification has a sobering effect on policy-making in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. The quantification method sets a minimum of standards for operational concepts which must be met by policy-makers. Operational concepts should be conceptually sound and coherent in terms of mandates, capabilities, resources, components, goals, tasks, exit strategies and actual impact. The introduction of a quantification method by itself is a symbolic act signalling that the mission / operation impact can and should be measured. Hence, this is a specific form of scientific control over EU policy-making in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding.

³⁹ Ron P. Smith, 'Quantitative Methods in Peace Research', *Journal of Peace Research* vol.35, no.4 (1998): 419-427.

6. Conclusion

The review of the operational concepts of three EU CSDP missions (EULEX Kosovo, EUTM Mali and EUBAM Libya) shows that all of them share common features. The essential features of EU operational concepts are: the mission type; mandate; capabilities; components; deficits; links with strategic concepts and policies, and exit strategy. Mandates are pivotal in operational concepts as they represent the EU's intentions and shape the respective mission / operation throughout its life-cycle. Hence, the project's method for decomposing operational concepts into quantifiable variables is based on mandates. The method converts mission / operational concepts into mandates, and then mandates into goals and tasks, which could be objectively measured by peace indicators. Peace indicators play a crucial role in the CDE4Peace quantification method as they are suitable for measuring the impact from EU missions and operations under the CSDP. They allow for measuring the attainment of mission goals and the accomplishment of mission tasks. Peace indicators in the CDE4Peace method entail three main components: 1) expert assessments; 2) public perception surveys; and 3) peace data on mission impact. When aggregated the three components provide valid and credible peace indicators. Despite the limitations of the quantification method it can serve as a specific form of scientific control over EU policy-making in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding.